

COMPETENCE-BASED APPROACH TO TEACHING MATHEMATICS TO PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS ACCORDING TO THE REQUIREMENTS IN THE NATIONAL CURRICULUM OF UZBEKISTAN

Dzhumaev Mamanazar Irgashevich

(PhD) pedagogical sciences, professor at Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after
Nizami

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10694172>

Abstract. *The minimum task that a teacher should perform in the development of creative quality in a student is to notice the transformation of the child's mental work from negative to positive, to make the educational environment psychologically comfortable for the child, and thus to understand the child's cognitive skills and prevent the emergence of new opportunities. . In fact, one of the most important ways to develop the creative potential of elementary school students is to focus on the creative expression of the child.*

Keywords: *mathematics, geometry, problem solving, national curriculum, education, formation, training.*

Mathematics is identified in our country as one of the priorities for the development of science in 2020, and a number of systemic measures are being implemented to promote the development of mathematical science and education to a new level. "The concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" was adopted on the basis of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5712 dated April 29, 2019, 9 July 2019 "Further development of mathematical education and science state support for development", Resolution No. PQ-4708 dated May 7, 2020 "On measures to improve the quality of education and develop scientific research in the field of mathematics". In particular, "The concept of development of mathematics education", contains contained in this program is designed to ensure the implementation of the assigned tasks for the comprehensive improvement of the above-mentioned mathematical education and its conclusion to a new quality level [3].

It is important to start the creative development of elementary school students with the ability to learn a lot of information, start with the development of combination and even imitation activities, because the activity is often creative at this age.

Therefore, it is important to give students the opportunity to create a model for the creative activity of students; It is important that the example applies not only to the product, but also to the activity. In other words, at the first stage of organizing creative activity, the child asks "what?" question to beep "how?" question should also be answered. In this case, it is possible to obtain a previously prepared type of product, it is better to understand the purpose of the work in advance, it is better to reproduce it (for example, you can show the students a movie showing the type of creation and the resulting type of product) [4-7].

In this case, imitation in reading itself is creative to a certain extent, in the context of the cover criticism of some knowledge; it requires an inner feeling, an unceasing mental initiative. No matter how simple the restrictions are, the interest of the students to know all the tricks will make a new trick.

According to Incon, knowing the program and the event with the important context, relationship and interaction of the person, in a direct and general way is the level of thinking, the most important multiplier of the development of the object. In psychology, it is used for multitasking-practical, multitasking-objective and abstract-conceptual thinking. The ability of students to think carefully is different from logical thinking.

One of the most important mechanisms of creativity is intuition. Modern psychology of creativity allows us to say that the inner feeling is the result of multiple layers. Here are the following:

1. Accumulation in the memory system and distribution in the unconscious mind.
2. Unconscious combination and processing of accumulated information and rules for solving a certain exercise.
3. Clearly understand the task.
4. Finding the solution to the task at once for a person. In most cases, such a solution suddenly comes to mind when the conscious activity of the brain is closed for solving other tasks, or even during sleep. So, when the task is set, the inner sense of the child can be activated only when the focus is shifted from the intellectual sphere to the emotional sphere. Controlling the inner feeling is the origin of the idea of reorganizing the emotional (emotional) and intellectual material. The teacher should keep this situation in mind. Let's focus on the important situation in which the inner feeling is connected to the Japanese poet, and in the preparation of the students, according to the purpose:

- to know creative Japanese language and use this knowledge in working with children;
- choosing the relevant information sheet when solving the exercise and determining the answer to the question;
- to come up with the connection between the elements of knowledge leading to the goal;
- to study the variety of ways of solving problems, to critically evaluate the solution, to choose the solution;
- getting out of the limits of previous knowledge by exploring the possible variety of knowledge elements and re-exaggerating the value of knowledge (using intra-disciplinary and inter-disciplinary connections).

We can determine the following way of brewing inner feeling: objective, intellectual and subjective, personal. Finally, we will write the following:

- application of the knowledge (additional questions, directional exercises, return and misshaped exercises white);
- use of the generalized method (method of reasoning, method of reasoning, method of cognitive activity);
- to compare existing knowledge;
- development of optical logical connection of concepts;
- variety of action steps;
- radical change of existing knowledge and experience;
- choosing the optimal tip;

The following is another group of internal feelings brewing:

- forget the environment by closing the eyes, putting the head on the hand, loosening the muscles and squinting;
- self-examination in order to determine the presence of an error;

- assessment of the heel of the step (exercises).

Just like music, inner feeling is not pleasing to everyone. Education that is not based on intuition and understanding leads to complacency and makes the student lose confidence in his own strength. Intuition is an important source of acquiring mathematical knowledge, an important factor that moves mathematical creativity forward. Intuitive thinking does not break the bounds of a fixed attitude, but rather reinforces and reinforces it.

This kind of gut-based approach is useful at the first level of education and has its value at the second level with a different approach. Understanding and understanding the essence of creative Japanese language (readers have a lot of it - humor and fantasy are very close to it) will make it easier to tell a large amount. Pupils are moved to know the elements of fantasy: an unexpected meeting for a girl, a natural story. The very novelty of the mental activity that is doing requires intuition and a unique mental initiative [8-10].

In the process of optimization, the formation of a new network and a network is based on the formation of a network, the network is divided into smaller segments, and a new network is created from the selected elements (character, network). Excitement does not feed speculation.

The essence of imaginary is to grasp the whole before the parts; the whole imagine is living separately, sometimes in small details. First of all, it is necessary to connect imagination activity with targeting the goal. It is not possible to know in advance the approximate result of the work being done, even if it is in the smallest amount. The formation of a future-oriented creative person takes place in the present-day concentrated creative process. By imagination or fantasy, we mean creative activity that relies on the combinational ability of our brain. He paid attention to the importance of developing creativity as a student. The task of creative imagination is to change the content of a previously created document in order to create a new document that can be copied and perform a new task.

According to pedagogues and methodologists, it is important to form an interest in learning, which is a valuable part of learning, in order to increase the activity and independence of students in learning (so that the child wants it). It is known that when we say motivation, we usually understand a set of desire for activity. This task is very difficult at the moment; because the motivation of studying diligently, such as knowledge, appreciation, and responsibility, has decreased.

REFERENCES

1. Djumaev M. Mathematical regularity and development of creative thinking of students.. Deutsche internationale Zeitschrift für zeitgenössische Wissenschaft / German International Journal of Modern Science. German International Journal of Modern Science. Edition: No. 28/2022 (February) – 28th Passed in press in February 2022 No. 28 2022. 26-28.
2. Dzhumaev M.I. Methodology for the emergence of a creative approach in pedagogy. materials international scientific and practical conference “Independent kazakhstan: modern educational potential and achievements”. 12/24/21. 124-128 art.
3. Dzhumaev M.I. Implementation of professional competence of teachers as a means of methodological and mathematical training in colleges. Vocational education of the Arctic regions No. 4/2022.7-9 Art.
4. Dzhumaev M.I. Improvement of effectiveness of methodological and mathematical preparation of a teacher of initial classes. Annali d’Italia (Italy’s scientific journal) is a peer-

- reviewed European journal covering top themes and problems in various fields of science. The journal authors offers the opportunity to make their research accessible to everyone, opening their work to a wider audience. VOL. 1 ISSN 3572-2436. №4 2020. 21-25. info@anditalia.com, ite: <https://www.anditalia.com/>
5. Dzhumaev M.I. The mechanism of the strategy of a new approach to the preparation of mathematics teachers in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Scientific, theoretical and practical journal “Vocational Education and Society” Moscow. 2020 No. 1(33) art. 81-188. kstP@edu.mos.ru
 6. Djumayev M.I The transformation of the English language’s variants in contemporary Great Britain. Educational process science and innovation international scientific journal volume 2 Issue 4 April 2023 Uif-2022: 8.2 | Issn: 2181-3337 | Scientists.Uz 19-27 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7818607>
 7. Djumaev M.I. Some Considerations of Teaching Mathematics Inuzbek Primary School. Journal of Mathematical & Computer Applications. SRC/JMCA-123. *J Mathe & Comp Appli*, 2023 Volume 2(2): 1-5 ISSN: 2754-6705
 8. Джумаев М.И. Перспективы совершенствования преподавания математики в школе, колледже и вузе Республики Узбекистан. Ямало-Ненецк Россия «Профессиональное образование арктических регионов» № 1, март, 2023. № 6(147) 3-6 ст <https://arctic-journal.ru/index.php/prof>
 9. Djumaev M.I. Some Considerations of Teaching Mathematics Inuzbek Primary School. Journal of Mathematical & Computer Applications. Received: March 28, 2023; Accepted: April 03, 2023, Published: April 22, 2023 ISSN: 2754-6705 1-5
 10. Djumaev M.I. Формирование элементарных математических представлений у детей в дошкольном возрасте с использованием и без наглядных материалов. Глобальный научный потенциал», ИД ТМБ принт, СПб. № 6 (147) 2023 г. <http://globaljournals.ru/>
 11. Dzhumaev Zh.M Scientific and practical foundations of studying the subject “Technology” in primary school. Professional education and society. — 2021. — No. 2(38). — 300 s. ISSN 2227-9652. 166-174
 12. Dzhumaev Zh.M Activation of forms and methods of teaching students in educational activities. Quarterly Scientific, theoretical and practical journal Professional education and society. Moskaa. - 2022. - No. 1 (41). — 300 s. ISSN 2227-9652 171-179
 13. Driga , V.I. Development of the professional career of a modern teacher in conditions of creative education / V.I. Driga // Standards and monitoring in education.— 2012.— No. 4.— P. 48–51
 14. Peterson L.G. Modeling as a means of formation before the representations of the concept of function in 4-6 classes of high school. Dis . for a job . student step. Cand. ped . sciences. -M., 1984. -201s.
 15. Dzhumaev M.E. Methods of teaching mathematics for elementary grades: a Textbook. Bayyoz. Tashkent, 2023 .-- 296 p.